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Review Article

REVIEW ON HERBS USED IN MOUTHWASH**Ayesha Siddiqua Gazi¹, Md Idris Ghori^{1*}, Syeda Umama Fatima², Ayesha Begum³,
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Abstract:

The goal of this study was to create formulations for mouthwash. An antibiotic, topical anti-inflammatory, topical painkiller, or caries prevention mouthwash could also be suggested.

Alcohol and fluoride, which are almost always found in ordinary mouthwash, are hazardous (even fatal) if ingested. With natural herbal mouthwashes, this is frequently not the case. Mouthwash can enter your circulation immediately after coming into contact with your mucosal membrane. Herbal mouthwash is made from natural plants including clove, peppermint, ajwain, green tea, neem, tulsi, and guava leaf.

Mouthwash can help fight tooth decay and prevent cavities in addition to fighting plaque and gingivitis and freshening breath. Mouthwash can significantly enhance your oral health It's employed within the subsequent cases: Halitosis, Mucositis, Periodontal Diseases, Gum disease, Xerostomia, To clean septic sockets, Reduce inflammation, Vincent's angina to control plaque, To relieve pain, To effectively deliver fluoride so on prevent dental cavity.

In spite of their everyday ability to promote good oral hygiene, herbal mouthwashes are less efficient than chlorhexidine mouthwash in treating conditions like gingivitis, periodontitis, trauma, etc.

Conclusion: Despite its drawbacks, chlorhexidine mouthwash is an excellent tool for short-term dental therapy. Natural mouthwashes can help you maintain healthy oral hygiene. It would take a lot of programmes to educate people about the importance of mouthwash in dental hygiene..

Keywords: Herbal, Mouthwash, Oral hygiene, Prophylaxis, gingivitis, periodontitis,

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INTRODUCTION:

Mouthwashes are liquids with analgesic, antibacterial, and anti-inflammatory properties. Mouthwash is a common remedy for its deodorising, cooling, and antibacterial qualities as well as for plaque management. Alcohol, glycerin, artificial sweeteners, surface-active ingredients, flavourings, colorings, etc.^[1,2] should all be present. Mouthwashes that eradicate 99.9% of oral bacteria also eradicate beneficial microorganisms. The microbiota of the mouth and its defences against cavities, gingivitis, and foul breath may be harmed as a result.

Advantages:

1. Fresh breath.
2. Using sodium fluoride to reduce tooth decay.
3. Taking out microorganisms to lessen gum irritation.
4. Using a bleaching product to whiten teeth
5. Using an antiseptic or anti-plaque substance to prevent gum disease.
6. Mouthwash stops the microorganisms that might otherwise cause gingivitis and gum disease.^[3,4,5]
7. It can demineralize your teeth, reinforce the enamel, and stop plaque formation, all of which help you prevent dental decay.^[6]

Herbal mouthwash has a number of advantages.

- Even the most sensitive lips can use herbal mouthwash without discomfort.
- Using herbal mouthwash is enjoyable.
- Natural ANTIBACTERIAL qualities exist in herbal mouthwash.
- There are no harmful components in herbal mouthwash.

- herbal mouthwash works well.
- Using a herbal mouthwash won't make you thirsty.
- Natural mouthwash includes no "mystery" components and is in high demand.

Natural Plants Used as herbal Mouthwash:**NEEM:****Synonyms:**

Hin.-Nira, nimb; Mal. – Veppa; Mar. – Limba, Oriya-Nimba; Tam- Vembu.

Biological Source: Neem consists of the fresh or dried leaves and seed oil of *Azadirachta indica* J. Juss (*Melia Indica* or *M. azadirachta* Linn.).

Family:

Meliaceae.

Geographical source:

It is found in India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Malaya, Indonesia, Japan, Tropical region of Australia and Africa. In India, it is found in Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Rajasthan, and M.P.

Macroscopical Characters:**Chemical Constituents:****1. Leaves:**

- i. Nimbin, 6- desacetylnimbinene.
 - ii. Nimbinene, Nimbandiol, nimbolide.
 - iii. Quercetin, β -sitosterol.
 - iv. Ascorbic acid, n-hexacosanol, nonacosane and amino acid.
- Nimbin & Nimbidinin.

2. Fruits:

- i. Gedunin.
- ii. 7-deacetoxy-7 α -hydroxygedunin.
- iii. Azadiredione, azadirone, nimbiol.
- iv. 17-epiazadiradione.

3. Seeds:

- i. Tetranortriterpenoids; 1, 2-diepoxyazadiradione,
- ii. 7-acetylneotrichilenone, 7-desacetyl-7-benzoylgedunin
- iii. Azadirachtin.

4. Oils:

- i. Fatty acid: Myristic acid, palmitic acid, stearic acid, oleic acid and linoleic acid.
- ii. Glycerides: Oleopalmitostearin, oleodistearin, odiolein and linoleodiolein.
- iii. Bitter principle: Nimbidin, nimbidinin, Nimbin, nimbinin and nimbidol.^[7]

CLOVE:

Synonyms: Clove buds, Clove flowers.

Biological Source

Clove consists of the dried flower buds of *Eugenia caryophyllus* Thumb., belonging to family Myrtaceae.

Geographical Source

Clove tree is a native of Indonesia. It is cultivated mainly in Islands of Zanzibar, Pemba, Brazil, Amboiana, and Sumatra. It is also found in Madagascar, Penang, Mauritius, West Indies, India, and Ceylon.

Chemical Constituents

Clove contains 14–21% of volatile oil. The other constituents present are the eugenol, acetyl eugenol, gallotannic acid, and two crystalline principles; α - and β -caryophyllenes, methyl furfural, gum, resin, and fibre. Caryophyllin is odourless component and appears to be a phytosterol, whereas eugenol is a colourless liquid. Clove oil has 60–90% eugenol, which is the cause of its anesthetic and antiseptic properties.

Uses:

As an antibiotic, stimulant, carminative, aromatic, and flavouring agent, clove is utilised. Antiemetic and anodyne are further uses for it. Clove oil is used by dentists as a root canal disinfectant and as an oral anaesthetic. Clove is used to treat diarrhoea, intestinal worms, and other digestive disorders because it kills intestinal parasites and has wide antibacterial capabilities against fungus and bacteria. Clove oil helps relieve dental pain. Eating cloves is claimed to have aphrodisiac properties, and a few drops of the oil in some water can halt vomiting. In modest quantities, eugenol is also employed as a local anaesthetic. The oil induces peristalsis and is an effective expectorant for bronchial issues in addition to being a potent germicide. Alkalies and aromatics work well in the infusion and clove water.^[8,9]

TULSI:**Synonyms:**

Sacred basil, Holy basil.

Biological Source:

Tulsi consists of fresh and dried leaves of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn., belonging to family Labiatae.

Geographical Source:

It is a herbaceous, much branched annual plant found throughout India, it is considered as sacred by Hindus. The plant is commonly cultivated in garden and also grown near temples. It is propagated by seeds. Tulsi, nowadays, is cultivated commercially for its volatile oil.

Chemical Constituents:

Tulsi leaves contain bright, yellow coloured and pleasant volatile oil (0.1 to 0.9%). The oil content of the drug varies depending upon the type, the place of cultivation and season of its collection. The oil is collected by steam distillation method from the leaves and flowering tops. It contains approximately 70% eugenol, carvacrol (3%), and eugenol-methyl-ether (20%). It also contains caryophyllin. Seeds contain fixed oil with good drying properties. The plant is also reported to contain alkaloids, glycosides, saponin, tannins, an appreciable amount of vitamin C and traces of maleic, citric, and tartaric acid.^[10,11]

PEPPERMINT:

Synonyms Oleummenthapiperita, Colpermin, Mentha oil.

Biological Source: The fresh blooming tips of the *Menthapiperita* Linn (family Labiatae) plant are steam-distilled to produce the oil. It is fixed if necessary. Not less than 4.5% and not more than 10% of menthyl acetate-calculated esters, not less than 44% of menthol-calculated free alcohols, and not less than 15% and not more than 32% of menthone-calculated ketone are all present in men

Chemical Constituents:

Depending on the variety, peppermint oil primarily contains menthol to the extent of 70% in free as well as esters form (like American, Japanese, Indian). Whereas Japanese peppermint oil has 70– 90% menthol, American peppermint oil has 80%. Menthone, menthofuran, jasmone,

menthylisovalerate, menthyl acetate, and several other terpene derivatives are also significant components of peppermint oil. The other terpenes are things like camphene, limonene, isopulegone, cineole, etc. Depending on the variety, peppermint oil contains +/- menthol mostly to the extent of 70% in free as well as in the form of esters (like American, Japanese, Indian). Japanese peppermint oil has 70– 90% menthol, compared to 80% in American peppermint oil. Menthone, menthofuran, jasmone, menthylisovalerate, menthyl acetate, and a number of other terpene derivatives are some of the peppermint oil's other significant components. Limonene, isopulegone, cineole, pinene, camphene, and other terpenes are among the additional terpenes. While menthofuran induces resinification and generates a foul smell, jasmone and esters are in charge of the flavor's pleasantness.^[12,13]

SPEARMINT :

Synonyms: Spearmint leaves, Mint, *Menthaviridis* Stotchspearmint, common spearmint.

Biological Source: This consists of dried leaves and flowering tops of the plant known as *Menthaspicate* Linn. (*Menthaviridis* Linn) or *Menthacardiaca* Geranol ex. Baker belonging to family Labiatae.

Geographical source: Spearmint is indigenous to Europe, but extensively cultivated in North America and Asia. More than 30,000 acres of land is under cultivation of spearmint in Washington state alone, Michigan, Indiana, Idaho, Yakima are the other places where it is cultivated commercially.

Chemical Constituents: It mostly contains volatile oil, around 0.5 to 1.0% resin, and tannins. Not less than 50% of the compound carvone, as well as trace amounts of pinene, cineole, and phellandrine, are present in spearmint oil. The plant is steam-distilled to produce spearmint oil, which is yellowish in color and has the distinctive minty scent. 0.930 to 0.940 specific gravity 48° to 59° of optical rotation 1.4820 to 1.4900 as the refractive index At least 50% of the oil's constituent, l-carvone, is present, with smaller amounts of linalool, pinene, cineole, and phelleandrene.

Uses:

Spearmint is used as carminative, flavour and source of spearmint oil is used as flavour mainly for tooth-pastes, mouth-washes, chewing gums and also for sauces and cosmetic products.^[14]

Uses of Mouthwash:

Mouthwashes should only be used for brief periods of sometime and can never be the sole means of oral hygiene.

It's employed within the subsequent cases:

- Halitosis
- Mucositis
- Periodontal Diseases
- Gum disease
- Xerostomia
- To clean septic sockets
- Reduce inflammation
- Vincent's angina to control plaque
- To relieve pain
- To effectively deliver fluoride so on prevent dental cavity

Evaluation:

Colour and scent: Visual inspection was used to assess physical characteristics such as colour and scent.

pH: Using a digital pH metre, the pH of produced herbal mouthwash was determined. One millilitre of mouthwash was weighed, diluted in fifty millilitres of pure water, and its pH was measured to calibrate the pH metre.^[15,16]

Check for microbiological development in mouthwash formulations: By using the streak plate approach, the created mouthwash was infected in the agar media plates while a control was made. The plates were put in the incubator, where they would stay for 24 hours at 37°C. Plates were removed from the incubation time and examined for microbial growth by comparing them to the control.^[17]

Tests for Quality Control on Specific Formulations:

quality assurance checks, Quality Control Tests for Selected Formulations: Quality control tests, including mouthwash pH, tannin content percentage, and essential oil yield were done on days 0 and 45, after preparation of formulations.^[18,19]

Stability Studies: The formulation and preparation of any pharmaceutical product is incomplete without proper stability studies of the prepared product. This is done in order to determine the physical and chemical stability of the prepared product and thus determine the safety of the product.^[20]

CONCLUSION:

Mouthwashes can be used for various conditions, depending on the lesions present in the oral cavity. Mouthwash is designed to help improve your oral hygiene and protect your gums from disease. An attempt has been made to stipulate variety of the commonly available herbs and plants, and certain fruits, which are readily available, and could be used as effective mouthwashes by all. If people can use and promote such cost-effective measures of maintaining the oral health which are innocent of any untoward side effects, it should help in overcoming some common dental problems.

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